

DIGITAL CAMPUSES IN ACADEMIC INSTITUTIONS FOR PROVIDING ON-LINE DIGITAL INFORMATION SERVICES TO THE ACADEMIC SOCIETY

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ABSTRACT

The Educational Organizations and Institutions are under constant pressure, from the ever growing academic challenging digital environment that compel Institutions to be more effective and adapt quick changes to the requirements to meet the present needs of the academic society. The present pandemic and digital environment lay a lot of emphasis on digital campuses towards addressing institutional growth, the changing student experience journey, industry engagement and learning outcomes. Since the main purpose of the library is to preserve and transmit the recorded knowledge, Libraries and librarians are inseparable from the society in which they serve and the society in which they live. In today's context of disruption from the pandemic, the strategic approach of institutions to address their digital transformation journey has raised the Digital campuses to face the on-line teaching and learning problems. The rise of digital campuses in the world of Education will look to address institutional challenges and provide insights on how academic institutions can successfully transform to digital campuses. This article explains what a digital campus is, why it is needful for the present digital environment and how can we establish a Digital campus to achieve the aim of the Institution. Also, what kind of digital resources may be connected and provided to the academic society have been explained to develop research outputs through Digital campus.

Key Words: Digital Campus, E-Resources, Digital online Learning, Academic Society, Digital Campus Management (DCM), DCM Skills.

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1. INTRODUCTION:

The Educational Organizations and Institutions are under constant pressure, from the ever growing academic challenging digital environment that compel Institutions to be more effective and adapt quick changes to the requirements to meet the present needs of the academic society. The higher education landscape is rapidly transforming due to the increased use of technology among students and staff. Now, rather than using technology as an extracurricular resource, digital solutions and platforms are deeply engrained in how students can learn and engage with others using digital online facilities. In today's context of disruption from the pandemic, the strategic approach of institutions to address their digital transformation journey has raised the Digital campuses to face the on-line teaching and learning problems. The rise of digital campuses in the world of Education will look to address institutional challenges and provide insights on how academic institutions can successfully transform to digital campuses.

2. WHAT IS A DIGITAL CAMPUS?

The higher education landscape is rapidly transforming due to the increased use of technology among students and staff. Now, rather than using technology as an extracurricular resource, digital solutions and platforms are deeply engrained in how students learn and engage with others. As more modern, digital technologies are increasing day to day, academic institutions are pressured to adopt and fully embrace more technology-driven ecosystems. Hence combining digitally-enabled Online courses with digital knowledge platforms and management in the Educational Institutions are known as Digital Campuses. [5]

A digital campus is an environment that collects information from students through their interactions and behaviours, converts it into meaningful data, and derives actionable insights. Considering that many colleges and universities are still offering remote classes, the digital campus covers virtual communities and classrooms as well. [10]

The Digital transformation converts a college into a **Digital Smart campus** and includes common infrastructures that:

- Offers digital assistance to students, such as push notifications, automated reminders & alerts for classwork, prep, and exams.
- Provides contextual summaries and recommendations to students and faculty based on their behaviours.
- Covers reliability, uptime, and other important services that have been the key components of digital transformation.

3. NEED FOR DIGITAL CAMPUS AND ONLINE INFORMATION SERVICES TO STUDENTS:

- The digital campus represents the full range of dematerialized services available to learners at every stage of their studies, which remains the heart of the information system. This is a major challenge for many educational establishments, whether universities, professional and continuing training organizations. It enables higher education Schools to enhance their image and attractiveness by offering each learner an individualized experience. [6]
- The digital campus combines teaching and technology in new education systems and it is a real digital device responding to the needs of higher education, the digital campus solution brings together the building blocks of a learner's lifecycle from applicant to alumni graduate.
- The Educational Organizations and Institutions are under constant pressure, from the ever evolving and challenging digital environment that force Institutions to be more effective and adapt quick changes to the requirements to meet the present digital needs of the society.
- Remote access to digital e-resources has long been a challenge for libraries. And the current situation, with more and more staff and students working from home, has only made the need for digital campus services more prominent.
- The digital campus combines teaching and technology in new School systems. A real digital device responding to the needs of higher education, the digital campus solution brings together the building blocks of a learner's lifecycle from applicant to alumni.
- Furthermore, digital campus service provides a consistent regular way for students to communicate with their teachers and improves safety and emergency communications in educational institutions.
- To support a successful online learning environment, the digital campus often includes broadband on campus and enables students to perform coursework through mobile platforms. In many cases, the digital campus also utilizes a cloud infrastructure to scale and secure online courses
- In today's world, technology must be incorporated into an institution's overall strategy and underlying infrastructure at a fundamental level. As online learning gains traction and fewer students return to campus in-person, colleges and universities need to prioritize digital experiences.

4. DIGITAL CAMPUS MANAGEMENT:

Digital campus management refers to the use of software and technology to streamline and automate administrative and academic operations within an educational institution. It includes a wide range of functions like admissions, student information management, attendance tracking, fee collection, course scheduling, and communication, all integrated into a single system. [9].

A "Digital Campus" is a virtual learning environment based on digital data, computer technology, and network infrastructure. It recognizes the data, the gathering, processing, integrating, storing, transmitting, and education, research, management, and other applications of campus technology services, to ensure that educational resources are available online. The

digital campus, in particular, employs modern information technology and tools to achieve digitalization from the environment such as devices and classrooms, as well as resources. [5]

4.1. CORE FUNCTIONS OF DIGITAL CAMPUS MANAGEMENT:

1. **Administrative management:** Digital administration handles tasks such as admissions, enrolment, document verification, and fee collection, often automating workflows and providing online portals for students and parents.
2. **Academic management:** Manages the curriculum, course registration, timetabling, attendance, and assessment processes. Some systems support outcome-based education and can facilitate both physical and online learning environments.
3. **Student lifecycle management:** Oversees the entire student journey from the initial application through to graduation, including managing student records, documents, and services.
4. **Communication:** Provides digital online communication tools for interaction between students, faculty, and parents, and can include features like campus help centers and automated notifications.
5. **Data and analytics:** Generates reports and dashboards from the data collected across different departments to aid in decision-making.

5. KEY COMPONENTS NEEDED FOR DIGITAL CAMPUS MANAGEMENT:

- ❖ **Integrated software platforms:** Centralized online systems that connect various functions like enrolment, academics, and administration.
- ❖ **High-speed internet and Wi-Fi:** Essential infrastructure to support all digital services.
- ❖ **Digital learning management systems (LMS):** Digital Platforms that facilitate online learning and content delivery.
- ❖ **Cloud-based applications:** Essential for data storage and accessibility from different devices.
- ❖ **Multimedia and interactive tools:** Used for creating and delivering teaching and learning content in classrooms and online facilities. [7]

6. HOW TO TRANSFORM EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS INTO A DIGITAL CAMPUS?

Creating and building a digital campus in higher education requires institutions to adopt modern technologies that deliver better online learning experiences and personalized student support to perform on-line learning coursework environment. Through Digital campus services academicians will get the graduating mind-set and never stop learning. Students can Unlock perpetual growth with Digital Campus services, the education that evolves within them, provided online by Digital Libraries. [10].

6.1. SKILLS NEEDED FOR DIGITAL CAMPUS MANAGEMENT:

For building a Digital Campus Management system in Institutions, the administration should have the following skills to improve the digital online teaching and learning environment.

6.1.1. Data Entry and Software Skills:

The administrators must know how to migrate data, upload new **online training content**, and use the software features to the team's advantage. They need to have experience with enrolling new learners into the **Learning Management System** and assigning roles.

Furthermore, admins should be familiar with the user interface dashboard, so that they can navigate the teaching and learning systems with ease. They need to know how to integrate the current software into the new Digital platform.

6.1.2. Project Management skills:

Admins need to have effective communication and teamwork skills in order to lead the teaching and learning systems effectively. They need to serve as Project Managers to assign online tasks, to track progress, and to handle staff and student requests on a regular basis. Time management and planning skills are essential for more involved online training projects with long-term objectives.

6.1.3. Tech Troubleshooting:

Tech trouble shooter is yet another important skill needed for Digital Campus admins. They must be able to solve software issues in order to make the most utilization of the online tools. The troubleshooting role also extends into the everyday activities of the staff and students of the academic institutions.

6.1.4. Problem solving skills:

The digital, software administrators should have the problem solving skill to ensure that the online training project runs smoothly and that everyone has the information they require. Problem solving is a crucial skill that allows the software managers to navigate obstacles, as well as deal with glitches of malfunctions before they become a widespread issue.

6.1.5. Interpersonal Skills:

Working with a diverse group of academic people may be a challenging task. Everyone has their own way of doing things, and sometimes different approaches which lead to on-the-job disagreements. Digital campus software managers need to enhance their interpersonal skills in order to resolve conflicts and provide collaborators with the support they require. They must be able to work well with others and make the most of individual strengths.

6.1.6. Analytical Skills:

Analytical skills involve creative reasoning and careful evaluation. The admins should be able to look at the situation from every angle, and then find the best approach. They must have the skill to use the available resources to achieve the desired outcomes and align with organizational objectives. This also involves a healthy measure of lateral thinking skills. In addition, they need to know how to allocate resources; namely human resources, assigning the right team members to the task based on their talents and abilities.

7. EXAMPLES OF FEW DIGITAL CAMPUS INSTITUTIONS:

1. CAMU DIGITAL CAMPUS, MALAYSIA:

Camu Digital Campus in Malaysia help Academic Institutions across the world to upgrade their education system and bring students closer to their career goals. Camu offers the Best in Class School and College Management system by leverages the power of technology, virtual Classroom technology, online Student Information System not only on Cloud –based platform compatible with newer models of learning, it also helps streamline academic and administrative processes efficiently and effectively. [7]

2. Best Digital Campus Management Systems & Software

Best campus management systems are Schoolcanvas.com, Teachmint, EDUMAAT, and Astral. All these campus management software and solutions are aimed at streamlining the routine operations of the institution and promoting a paperless environment [9]

3. BLUNEST

Blunest Technologies, a robust worldwide technology team headquartered at Pune, Maharashtra, India. In time where the Covid-19 pandemic has put the World on hold, it has leveraged online learning system to ensure that academic activities are not paused. To ensure that formal education continues to be in flow, Blunest Technologies brings Online Learning Management System.

4. IISC, BANGALORE: Digital Campus and Information Technology Services (DIGITS)

DIGITS (Digital Campus and IT Services) Office is a unit set up by the Institute to conceive, plan, and create a best-in-class information technology (IT) and networking system, and implement agile IT and networking services for operational excellence in the Institute. [10]. The **DIGITS** office will consolidate and coordinate all digital campus activities and services for better execution of the following initiatives in IISc:

- OPERA (Operational Excellence for Research Advancement)
- CCIT (Committee on Computerisation and Information Technology)
- TINA (Telecom, Internet, and Network Access)
- VISE (Video Security Equipment for IISc)
- MMCR (Multimedia Class Rooms Initiative)
- Video archives and streaming
- IISc webpage development and maintenance
- Campus infrastructure data acquisition and analytics

8. ADVANTAGES OF DIGITAL CAMPUS SERVICES:

- ❖ Through Digital campus services, the academicians will get the graduating encouraged mind-set and never stop learning.
- ❖ Students can Unlock perpetual growth with Digital Campus services, the education that evolves within them, provided online by Digital Libraries.
- ❖ Digital campus online service embraces and encourage the lifelong learner and the journey of learning will never end.
- ❖ Digital campus service expertizes multidisciplinary learning experiences to the faculties and students.
- ❖ Digital Campus for an educational institution resonates, powerful skills, business communication performance, and personal growth.
- ❖ Access learning activities, videos and quizzes all offline on Android smartphones. Supports learning/training content for any professional area.

9. Benefits of Digital Campus to Staff and Students:

1. Enhanced Student Experiences:

For the tech-savvy and well-connected generation, **Digital transformation in higher education** includes virtual health services, voice-activated assistance, real-time occupancy system, food kiosks, contactless payment, etc. with high level of accessibility to intuitive and hassle-free services. With interactive, automated, and immersive technology, learners can personalise their environment.

2. Safe College Campus:

The safety of students on college campuses has always been a major concern for parents, students, and faculty. Traditional methods with good lighting and round-the-clock patrolling are no more effective to assure protection. Hence, Digital campus are integrating internet-based security systems that reduce campus crimes and increase awareness among students. Universities now have AI-powered technologies, such as wireless sensors, smart IP video cameras, smart trackers, and more to safeguard people and assets. [8]

3. Cost-effective Operations

When university buildings and utilities are connected to smart technologies, it reduces overall operational costs. Automation and digitization mitigates manual tasks and chances of errors while saving time and efforts of administrators that can be redirected to other important activities.

4. **Digital transformation in the education sector** assures data-driven decisions in colleges that are based on real-time information and facts.
5. **Increased efficiency:** Automates repetitive tasks, reducing errors and the administrative burden on staff.
6. **Improved experience:** Provides students and parents with convenient access to information and services through online portals.
7. **Data-driven decisions:** Offers real-time insights through reports and analytics to help administrators make informed choices.
8. **Enhanced collaboration:** Connects different departments and stakeholders, fostering seamless collaboration.

10. CHALLENGES IN DIGITAL CAMPUS MANAGEMENT:

- The challenges of disruption from technology leading to Digital Campus Education, has only increased with the pandemic. Digital preservation to ensure the successful digital campus services and information systems are still interpretable challenge into the indefinite ever growing digital future. [8]
- To develop and ensure the present expectations in academic institutions, digital online Education policies and regulatory frameworks are very much essential to address the changing dynamics to ensure successful student outcomes.
- Therefore, for balancing the varying needs across Compliance, Accreditation, faculty enrichment and student expectations in the context of the Digital environment, technology adoption using strategic methods like flexible learning through online as well as transforming the academic institutions to digital campuses is very much essential.
- To meet the present challenges of digital and artificial intelligence based education the Digital Campus Management system is a real essential digital online system which responding to the needs of faculty and students of higher education.

11. CONCLUSION:

The Educational Organizations and Institutions are under constant pressure, from the ever evolving and challenging digital environment that force Institutions to be more effective and adapt quick digital changes to meet the present digital needs of the requirements of the educational society. As online digital learning system gains traction and fewer students return to campus in-person, colleges and universities need to prioritize digital experiences. Remote access to digital e-resources has long been a challenge for libraries in academic institutions.

And the current situation, with more and more staff and students working from home, has only made the need for digital campus services more prominent. Since digital campus service provides a consistent regular way for students to communicate with their teachers and improves safety and emergency communications in educational institutions, Digital Campus Management is very much essential to improve and fulfil the aims of the academic institutions.

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